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Prevalence of Periodontal Disease, Its Association with Systemic Diseases, and Prevention

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Abstract

Periodontal disease is a prevalent oral health issue affecting a significant portion of the global population. The multifactorial etiology of periodontal disease involves dysregulated host responses to microbial biofilm, leading to progressive tissue destruction, ranging from reversible gingivitis to irreversible stages impacting periodontal ligament and alveolar bone. Variations in disease prevalence among populations underscore the influence of factors like age, gender, and socioeconomic status. Emphasizing the pivotal role of effective oral hygiene practices, this review delves into the global prevalence of periodontal disease, noting regional disparities influenced by cultural practices, socioeconomic conditions, and healthcare accessibility. Here we also explore the bidirectional relationship between periodontal disease and systemic conditions, focusing on diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, and rheumatoid arthritis.

Keywords: Periodontal Disease, Oral Hygiene, Diabetes Mellitus, Cardiovascular Diseases, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Preventive Strategies

1. Introduction:

Periodontal disease, characterized by inflammation of the supporting structures of the teeth, is a common oral health problem worldwide. The prevalence of periodontal disease varies among different populations, with factors such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status influencing its occurrence (Petersen et al., 2005). The multifactorial etiology of periodontal disease involves a dysregulated host response to the

microbial biofilm, leading to the destruction of periodontal tissues. This destructive process encompasses gingivitis, an early reversible stage characterized by inflammation of the gingiva and can progress to irreversible stages involving periodontal ligament and alveolar bone (Tonetti et al., 2018).

The intricate interplay of genetic predisposition, environmental factors, and microbial composition contributes to the heterogeneity in disease manifestation and progression. Effective oral hygiene practices, encompassing meticulous plaque control through regular brushing and flossing,

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represent the cornerstone of periodontal disease prevention (Cobb, 2006). Furthermore, lifestyle modifications, including smoking cessation and adoption of a balanced diet, play pivotal roles in mitigating risk factors associated with periodontal disease.

2. Prevalence of Periodontal Disease:

The global prevalence of periodontal disease has been extensively investigated through numerous studies, shedding light on the considerable burden it poses to public health. In a seminal global oral health survey conducted by Kassebaum et al. (2017), it was revealed that severe periodontitis impacts approximately 10% of the world's population. This estimate underscores the widespread nature of the disease and its significance in the context of global oral health. Importantly, the survey also identified variations in prevalence between different regions and countries, emphasizing the multifactorial nature of periodontal disease epidemiology.

The regional and country-specific differences in prevalence highlight the influence of diverse factors such as cultural practices, socioeconomic conditions, and access to oral healthcare. For instance, populations in poor regions may face increased challenges in accessing dental care, potentially contributing to higher prevalence rates. Conversely, regions with robust healthcare infrastructures and preventive measures may exhibit lower prevalence rates. Understanding these variations is crucial for tailoring public health interventions to address the unique challenges posed by periodontal disease in different global contexts.

Moreover, age has emerged as a pivotal risk factor in the prevalence of periodontal disease. The landmark study by Eke et al. (2016) emphasizes this association by demonstrating a positive correlation between age and the prevalence of periodontitis. The implications of aging on periodontal health are multifaceted, involving factors such as cumulative exposure to risk factors, changes in immune response, and the cumulative impact of chronic inflammation over time. The prevalence of severe periodontal disease tends to increase significantly in older age groups, underscoring the importance of age as a critical risk factor.

Age-related changes in the oral microbiome and host response mechanisms contribute to an environment conducive to the development and progression of periodontal disease. Shifts in the composition of the oral microbiota, coupled with diminished regenerative capacities of periodontal tissues, create an environment where the pathogenic processes associated with periodontitis can thrive. As individuals age, there is often an increased susceptibility to systemic conditions, which may further exacerbate the interplay between periodontal disease and overall health.

3. Association with Systemic Diseases:

Mounting evidence suggests a bidirectional relationship between periodontal disease and systemic conditions. Chronic inflammatory processes in periodontal tissues may contribute to the development or exacerbation of systemic diseases (Sanchez et al., 2014). Diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, and rheumatoid arthritis have been extensively studied in this context.

3.1 Diabetes Mellitus:

The intricate interplay between diabetes mellitus and periodontal disease represents a compelling example of a bidirectional relationship, wherein the conditions reciprocally influence and exacerbate each other. A comprehensive understanding of this interaction involves delving into the molecular and immunological underpinnings that underscore the complex interrelationship between these two prevalent chronic conditions.

Individuals afflicted with diabetes mellitus exhibit an elevated susceptibility to periodontal disease, a phenomenon well-supported by empirical evidence (Chavarry et al., 2013). The diabetic milieu, characterized by chronic hyperglycemia, creates an environment conducive to the proliferation of pathogenic bacteria within the oral cavity. Hyperglycemia impairs the host's immune response, compromising the ability to mount an effective defense against microbial invaders. This immune dysregulation includes impaired neutrophil function, reduced chemotaxis, and compromised phagocytosis, all of which contribute to a compromised host defense mechanism in individuals with diabetes (Lalla et al., 2013).

Conversely, the periodontal disease-associated inflammatory response poses a unique set of challenges for individuals with diabetes, leading to implications for glycemic control. Chronic inflammation, a hallmark of periodontal disease, is characterized by the release of proinflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and interleukin-6 (IL-6) into the systemic circulation (Mealey & Oates, 2006). These cytokines can induce insulin resistance at the cellular level, thereby compromising insulin sensitivity and contributing to poor glycemic control in individuals with diabetes.

Moreover, the inflammatory cascade in periodontal tissues stimulates the release of acute-phase proteins, including C-reactive protein (CRP), which has been implicated in insulin resistance and endothelial dysfunction (Lalla et al., 2003). Elevated levels of CRP in response to periodontal inflammation may further contribute to the systemic inflammatory burden in diabetes, fostering a proatherogenic environment.

The heightened systemic inflammatory state may exacerbate existing cardiovascular risk factors, compounding the challenges associated with managing diabetes in affected individuals.

Furthermore, the molecular mechanisms linking periodontal disease and diabetes involve the activation of various intracellular signaling pathways. The receptor for advanced glycation end-products (RAGE) and nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) pathways are implicated in both diabetes and periodontal disease (Lalla et al., 2003; Hajishengallis & Chavakis, 2021). These shared pathways underscore the intricate signaling crosstalk that contributes to the bidirectional relationship between these conditions.

The cumulative impact of periodontal disease on diabetes management extends beyond glycemic control, encompassing systemic complications. Periodontal disease-induced systemic inflammation may exacerbate diabetic complications, including cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, and retinopathy (Preshaw et al., 2012). As such, the bidirectional relationship between diabetes mellitus and periodontal disease underscores the need for an integrated approach to healthcare, where oral health considerations are seamlessly woven into the broader management strategies for individuals with diabetes.

3.2 cardiovascular diseases:

Chronic periodontal inflammation, characterized by the dysregulation of the host immune response to the microbial biofilm, has been implicated as a potential contributor to the development and progression of atherosclerosis, a key pathological process in cardiovascular diseases (Tonetti et al., 2017). Atherosclerosis is a chronic inflammatory condition marked by the accumulation of lipids, immune cells, and fibrous tissue within arterial walls. The inflammatory mediators released during periodontal disease, such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), may enter the bloodstream and contribute to systemic inflammation, thereby fostering a proatherogenic environment.

Moreover, the oral microbiome, which undergoes compositional changes in the context of periodontal disease, has been implicated in the seeding of bacteria into systemic circulation. Bacterial products, including lipopolysaccharides (LPS) and bacterial DNA, may translocate into the bloodstream, eliciting systemic inflammatory responses and potentially contributing to endothelial dysfunction—a precursor to atherosclerosis (Kozarov et al., 2005). The infiltration of immune cells into atherosclerotic plaques further amplifies the inflammatory burden, linking the localized inflammation in the periodontium to systemic vascular pathology.

Clinical studies have provided compelling evidence supporting the association between periodontal disease and an increased risk of cardiovascular events. A meta-analysis by Lockhart et al. (2012) reported a significant association between periodontal disease and coronary heart disease, reinforcing the clinical relevance of this link. The precise mechanisms through which periodontal disease may contribute to specific cardiovascular events, such as myocardial infarction or stroke, continue to be a subject of ongoing research.

Common risk factors further emphasize the interconnectedness of oral and systemic health in the context of periodontal disease and cardiovascular diseases. Inflammation, a hallmark of both conditions, serves as a unifying factor that amplifies the risk of systemic complications. The systemic inflammatory burden arising from periodontal disease may synergize with other inflammatory conditions, creating an environment

conducive to the development and progression of cardiovascular diseases (Genco and Borgnakke, 2020). Additionally, smoking, a well-established risk factor for both periodontal disease and CVD, further underscores the intricate interplay of shared risk factors.

3.3 Rheumatoid Arthritis:

Inflammatory cascades play a central role in both rheumatoid arthritis and periodontal disease, providing a common ground for potential interactions. Rheumatoid arthritis is characterized by systemic inflammation, autoimmune responses, and synovial tissue inflammation, ultimately leading to joint destruction (McInnes & Schett, 2011). Periodontal disease, on the other hand, involves chronic inflammation within the supporting structures of the teeth, driven by the host response to bacterial biofilms (Tonetti et al., 2018). The convergence of these inflammatory pathways raises intriguing questions about the potential systemic consequences and bidirectional influences on disease progression.

Epidemiological studies have consistently demonstrated a higher prevalence of periodontitis in individuals with rheumatoid arthritis compared to those without the autoimmune condition (Scher et al., 2014). The association between these two conditions suggests that the inflammatory burden characteristic of rheumatoid arthritis may extend beyond the joints, influencing the oral environment and predisposing individuals to periodontal disease. The potential impact of oral health on systemic inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis patients highlights the need for integrated healthcare strategies that consider both the musculoskeletal and oral health aspects of these individuals.

The mechanisms linking rheumatoid arthritis and periodontal disease are not fully elucidated, and further research is imperative to unravel the intricate molecular pathways involved. Several hypotheses have been proposed, including the role of shared inflammatory mediators such as cytokines and the potential impact of the altered immune response observed in rheumatoid arthritis.

Cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), are central players in the inflammatory processes of both rheumatoid arthritis and

periodontal disease. These cytokines orchestrate immune responses, tissue destruction, and remodeling, and their dysregulation can contribute to the perpetuation of inflammation in diverse anatomical sites (Bartold & Marshall, 2015). The systemic circulation of these inflammatory mediators may serve as conduits for the crosstalk between joints and oral tissues, providing a potential mechanistic link between rheumatoid arthritis and periodontal disease.

Furthermore, alterations in the immune response observed in rheumatoid arthritis, characterized by autoantibody production and aberrant T-cell activation, may impact the susceptibility to periodontal pathogens and the magnitude of the inflammatory response within the oral cavity (Bartold & Marshall, 2015). The potential bidirectional influence of periodontal disease on rheumatoid arthritis progression and vice versa remains an area of active investigation.

4. Prevention of Periodontal Disease:

Preventive strategies play a crucial role in managing periodontal disease. Effective oral hygiene practices, including regular brushing, flossing, and professional dental cleanings, are fundamental in preventing the onset and progression of periodontal disease (Cobb, 2006). Additionally, lifestyle modifications, such as smoking cessation and a healthy diet, contribute to overall oral health.

5. Conclusion:

Periodontal disease, a widespread oral health concern, carries implications for systemic well-being. A comprehensive understanding of its prevalence and association with systemic diseases is essential for a thorough approach to healthcare. Vital to the management of periodontal disease and its impact on systemic health are preventive measures, encompassing not only oral hygiene practices but also lifestyle modifications. In the broader healthcare context, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration between oral health professionals and practitioners in other medical fields is paramount. This collaborative approach, driven by an appreciation of the connections between periodontal disease and systemic conditions, lays the groundwork for holistic healthcare strategies. As ongoing research unveils

the intricate molecular pathways and shared inflammatory mediators linking these entities, the seamless integration of oral health considerations into broader healthcare management becomes imperative. Emphasizing preventive strategies, with a focus on routine oral care practices and lifestyle adjustments, is key to addressing the global burden of periodontal disease and recognizing its potential systemic implications.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.